

ABOUT THE CATEGORY "CLOTHES/DRESSES"

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Abstract. *In this article, the concept of category, etymological, semantic and stylistic features specific to the category of clothes/dresses are discussed.*

Keywords: *category, classification, categorization, stimulus, concept, sphere, clothing, dress, figurative meaning.*

It is known that the concept of category is interpreted in a very broad sense, and it reflects the most general and important qualities, characteristics, connections and relations of the objects and phenomena of reality. The practice of dividing objects and events into categories and classifying them into groups has existed since ancient times. But finding classification symbols and dividing categories based on them was often done simply, based on personal experience, in a simple style, with a human appearance. As L.V. Barsalou [1, 102] noted, categorization is a complex mental and linguistic process.

This process includes certain types of action steps:

- a) choice of stimulus (inciting cause). Only those that attract attention are selected from the stimuli that enter the sensory system (such as sight, hearing, smell);
- b) separation and classification. This action is performed by comparing and matching the selected stimulus with the knowledge in memory;
- c) naming. The resulting cognitive category (concept) is named.

All objects in reality have an orderly structure. Basically, the goal of gaining more information with less cognitive effort is achieved by means of a category system that clearly reflects the structure of the perceived piece of reality. In particular, it is appropriate to approach the category of clothing in the language in the same way.

Clothing is a head covering that partially covers a person's body and head. It is made of soft, non-abrasive, processed and unprocessed material of leather or plant. Its shape is in accordance with the body structure of a person. "Clothes, according to their purpose, arose as a result of a person's need to protect his body from the adverse effects of the environment.

Its fundamental difference from other things is not in form and material, but in the nature of being used in connection with some social activity" [2, 14].

The historical development of the meaning of the word "clothing" shows that this name in its current meaning, but in different phonetic forms, is written in Orhun-Yenisei from the monuments to the 13th - 14th centuries, it is found in the form of *kädım//küzım, kädgu//küzgu*, generally in the sense of a dress worn on top and in various subtleties of meaning. Examples: *ynchyn ynantym ash tön kädım orün tyushak at janga kanly kölu apdını-jangü* (food and clothes, dresses, comfortable accommodation and for horses, elephants, carts and beasts of burden) (Malov, 21); *közgü*—everything that is worn (DLT, I, 405); I need to drink a ton of wine when I'm sleeping (Makhmudov, 63); *Shirin* dialed the tones of the legs and hips (Fazylov. 1, 575); *kikiduk* - headdress made of veil (DLT, 1, 371); *kizuk* - a covering worn in the rain (DLT, I, 371); *Kejuk* is a rain cover made of felt (DLT, III, 182) [3, 16].

In Tafsir, a written monument of the 12th-13th centuries, it was found that along with the verb forms *köz, közar* (r. *odevat*), there are also the forms *käjb, käjmak* from the root of *kiy, küür*, from the verb stem *käj* (144, 178).

The transition of *kädím//küzím* variant to *kayim*, clothing pronunciation in Old Uzbek language was correctly identified by prof. S.E. Malov. The forms *kädím // küzím* are not found in the language of Alisher Navoi's works (15th century). In his works, Navoi used the root of this name in the form of *ki*, the name of clothing is *kiyguluk*, and the infinitive form is *kiyum*: A man's adornment is wisdom. Good clothes are a comfort to women (Navoi, MQ).

In the 19th and 20th centuries, the words *clothes, dresses, top-head, light, light-head, head-shoes, shirt, kisvat* were used for clothes.

Clothes and dress are synonyms. The concept of clothing is standardized in dress. Therefore, although the range of meaning of clothes seems to be wider than that of a dress, in fact, the conceptual sphere of a dress can be expanded as desired.

Libos is an Arabic word (plural *libosot*) [4, 336] and is characteristic of the high style of the literary language. The word "*libos*" can be synonymous with the word "*clothing*" in the light sense. The word "*clothes*" is a common neutral word in the lexicon of the common language and is used in literary and colloquial language. The word "*libos*" is more characteristic of written artistic speech. The dress is not found in the oldest written monuments of the Turkic language.

This word is used in "*Hibat ul-haqayq*", which is considered a written monument of the 12th century: *Tanabbur libasyn këyip az salin* (Ahmed Yugnakiy).

In the work "*Gulistoni bit Turki*" the word "*libos*" is used in the sense of outer clothing: *Nech kim dalq erur arif libosy, mubarakdur, khaloyqqa duosi* (Saifi Saroi).

By the 15th century, instead of the word *clothes*, the word *dress* was widely used in literary works for stylistic purposes. He sewed a dress from a bullet needle, and a dagger killed him (Navoi).

Also: *Turfa oyedur uzoring, blue dress for blue, Anjum is gold printed on coins* (Navoiy, FS); If you say, your food will not be wasted, and if you wish, your clothes will not wear out, wear them (Navoiy, MQ).

In Navoi's works, the word "*libos*" was combined with a defining word, the range of meaning was expanded, and it acquired different nuances of meaning through analogy.

For example: a beautiful dress is a beautiful, fitting dress: Get rid of the thought of a beautiful dress, if you want a beautiful dress, wear a naked dress (Navoi, MQ).

In speech, the word "*clothing*" has a wider semantic field compared to "*dress*". Because the word *dress* is interpreted in national, philosophical, and religious terms in different metaphorical meanings in people's thinking, language memory. For example, Husayn Boygaro, acknowledging Alisher Navoi's great services in the development of the literary language: "The dead body of the Turkic language was breathed into a soul by the breath of Christ, and that spirit gave those who found it a *hulla* and *harir* woven from Turkic language". From this recognition comes the meaning that Alisher Navoi gave Turkic language a new life and a classic spirit, because Christ is the one who gives a new life and a classic spirit to a dead body.

The poet dressed this new soul in beautiful silk clothes woven from the weaving of the Turkic language. He says that until Navoi, no one was able to put such beautiful Turkic clothes on the body of "*virgin meanings*" [5,122]. In fact, there is no exaggeration in these thoughts poetically expressed by Husayn Boygaro.

Dressing the beautiful and silken clothes woven from the weave of Turkic language in the virgin meanings of the classical spirit is directly related to the problems of the artistic language that we are analyzing.

Such metaphorical meanings of the word clothing are observed in the Qur'anic chapter "Baqarah" in the statement that husband and wife are clothes for each other: "...They are clothes for you, and you are clothes for them" (verse 187). And in Surah "Naba'" the word `libos' refers to the night and expresses the concepts of `rest" and `huzur": "And We made your sleep pleasant (verse 9); And we clothed the night (verse 10)".

Rumi says, "Allah has His servants clothed in the garments of wisdom, enlightenment, and blessings. Even if the people do not have sharp eyes to see these things, Allah Almighty will make them angry. They also behave like Mutanabbi: "Women don't wear silk clothes to adorn themselves, but to show off their beauty."

They wear it to protect themselves", they wrap it (with clothes of wisdom, enlightenment and grace)" [6,12].

It can be observed that the concept of clothes is used figuratively not only in the artistic style, but also in the scientific style, in particular, it is attributed to thinking: "Thinking cannot be naked." This sacred event should always be worn. Therefore, when imagining the composition of mental structures and even their content, we involuntarily turn to language and its specific tools" [7,44].

The main task of cognitive linguistics is to study the mental processes that take place in the human mind in connection with linguistic activity. In this regard, one of the main achievements of this science is the "traces" of previous experience formed in memory as a result of human cognitive activity [7, 53], that is, the definition of categorical concepts and logical and linguistic systems of high-level content structures of various forms is the collection of data sets. The integrity of the connection between these two systems is clearly reflected in the phenomenon of categorization.

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